

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHONETICS IN LEARNING ENGLISH, AS WELL AS DIFFICULTIES IN MASTERING IT

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ABSTRACT

the article is devoted to the disclosure of phonetics and grammar in the process of learning English. It names the forms of work and requirements.

In learning English, it is necessary to pay special attention to its phonetics and grammar. A lesson in practical phonetics usually begins with a complex phonetic charge, which includes either exercises for the development of phonetic hearing, speech rhythm, speech techniques or phrases or small texts aimed at working out sounds and ways of connecting them in the flow of speech. The work is usually carried out frontally and takes no more than 15-20 minutes.

The introduction of the main topic of the lesson is recommended to be carried out with the involvement of educational research work of students, while it is advisable to use listening to phonetic material with subsequent analysis and formulation of conclusions or rules.

In high school, great attention is paid to intonation tools when teaching foreign languages. Without mastering the sound system of the language, the reader will not be able to use this language as a means of communication. Correctly formed speech skills and qualifications imply the ability to speak, read and write in a foreign language, that is, to understand this language with verbal perception. To form phonetic skills, it is necessary not only to be able to pronounce sounds correctly, but also to know the rules for combining these words into sentences. Pronunciation skills are not speech skills, because you can pronounce not only phrases and words, but also simple sounds, whether they are necessary for speech or not. From another point of view, pronunciation does not include speech skills, since it is impossible to write, speak, listen or read without articular movements of the oral apparatus. On this basis, we can conclude that the formation of phonetic skills begins with the organizational or self-formation of pronunciation skills. Direct pronunciation skills should be formed from the initial stages of learning a foreign language and, if necessary, this action should be continued with one or another saturation coefficient.

How does phonetics occupy a place in a number of linguistic disciplines? This question has found a different solution in linguistics. Some saw phonetics as part of grammar, others as an

independent science. The second solution already has more bases, since phonetics works with non-pointing, one-sided units, units of the plane of expression: neither phonemes, nor sounds that manifest these phonemes (their specific representatives), as mentioned above, have no meaning, while the units of all other syllables starting with morphemes have meaning and are therefore character units. Phonetics is the only science that is the subject of the study of the sound matter of language. Not all other disciplines are interested in the material side of their plan units: they pay attention to the peculiarities of the structural and semantic side of morphemes, words, phrases, sentences.

The study of phonetics is of great theoretical and practical importance. The theoretical significance lies in the fact that the phonetic-phonological line is the main branch of the language, the specific foundation on which the construction of the entire language will be based: morphemes, words and sentences are embodied in sounds. Consequently, it is impossible to study neither the lexical nor grammatical structure of a language without studying phonetics.

The phonological study of phonetics provides the basis for the formation of the scientific worldview of the philologist, the "experimental field of linguistics". Phonetics "teaches the young philologist to understand that language is a single, harmonious, intelligent, internally consistent integrity. The molds of language are easier to understand in phonetics because phonetics itself is simpler than vocabulary and grammar".

The definition of the word "phonetics" lies in the name itself, which is derived from the Greek background - "sound". The object of study of phonetics is sound speech, starting with sounds and ending with a sound text. Hence, phonemes, stress in Word and sentence, syllable making and syllable division, intonation fall into the field of study of phonetics. Phonetics is a branch of linguistics that studies the nature, development and semantic functions of the sound matter of a language.

At first glance, it may seem that phonetics only affects the plan for expressing language, but this is not the case. Phonetics cannot exist separated from meaning, since at any stage of analysis the phonetic is primarily interested in how the properties of the unit of expression he is studying affect its meaning.

Phonetics is one of the main, but also one of the most basic areas of linguistics. No linguistic theory and practice can be realized without phonetics, and no description of a language is complete and complete without phonetics. Therefore, phonetics is at the same level as grammar and lexicology.

Phonetics sections

There are several aspects of phonetics. First of all, articulatory (physiological), acoustic, perceptual.

Articulatory phonetics is the branch of phonetics that deals with the study, description and classification of sounds in terms of pronunciation, that is, sounds, in the result of the work of speech organs. This section of phonetics describes the movement of air along the sound paths, the Coordination of speech organs in the process of pronouncing individual sounds. It is one of the oldest and most fully studied sections of phonetics.

Acoustic phonetics (phonoacoustics) is closely related to the acoustics branch of physics. For acoustic phonetics, information about the acoustic properties of speech flow is important: frequency, force (intensity), time of vibrational movements that create a sound wave. Acoustic

phonetics is the youngest and fastest growing field of phonetics. It is of particular interest for scientific work on experimental phonetics and Applied Linguistics.

Perceptual phonetics is designed to study the features of the perception of sound units. In the process of perception of speech sounds, he studies the activity of various parts of the auditory system and the upper nerve, as well as what signs determine the belonging of sound to a particular phoneme, how unfamiliar language sounds are perceived. For a subject who perceives and does not perceive human speech, sound properties are important (the effect of sound color on perception, telephone noise, speech errors, noise). Perceptual phonetics is of great interest to all pronunciation students, both teachers and students.

Special attention should be paid to working out the main sounding text of this topic. Its study usually goes through the stages of introduction, primary and secondary consolidation.

The main intonation models of the text (intonation of the main communicative types of utterance, models of attracting attention, invitations to continue a conversation in a dialogical text) should be fixed on the material of reading self-prepared passages or in oral work at a training session, including preparatory and speech exercises. Speech exercises are a mandatory component of the final stage of the lesson.

Practical development of phonetic material is accompanied by the study of theoretical provisions on each topic. Testing of knowledge on the phonetics of the English language is carried out both in the form of questions and answers, and in the form of a practical task of an analytical nature. The study of the topic can be completed with a control work, which is a prerequisite for ensuring the strength of students' assimilation of the acquired knowledge in English classes. You can also add to it the development of exercises on the topics being studied. They must meet the following requirements:

- a) ensure regular verification of students' assimilation of the lesson material;
- b) be optimal in terms of execution time, which is especially important for classes performed in the classroom;
- c) contain a series of repetitive tasks by type (in order to reduce the study time to explain the requirements for their implementation);
- d) contain both classroom and extracurricular tasks.

It is recommended to carry out control work after studying certain topics with subsequent analysis of the results. This allows not only to reveal the picture of students' assimilation of knowledge, but also to re-examine the most difficult issues.

In the process of conducting practical grammar classes, special attention should be paid to the fact that the section of practical grammar of the language is a single complex combining classroom classes with independent work of students in order to form their skills of correct use of grammatical phenomena in oral and written speech, creating a fully formed speech work in accordance with the communicative task of the speech act.

Improving the teaching of practical grammar is closely related to such principles of optimizing the educational process as the rejection of the authoritarian style of teaching and orientation to the personal qualities of students. The formation of grammatical concepts should occur when teaching grammar not in the form of lectures, but in practical terms, on specific language material.

The practice of teaching grammar shows that not only comparisons with the native language are productive, but also comparisons of similar grammatical phenomena of other languages,

which refers to the consciously comparative method of teaching grammar.

The skills and abilities of students in the field of practical grammar should be evaluated not only from the point of view of the strength and flexibility of grammatical skills and abilities, i.e. from the qualitative side, but also from the quantitative side, which consists in a set of those situational-speech stereotypes of the use of this grammatical phenomenon that the student possesses [1, p. 16]. The most important way of mastering a language is speech practice in oral and written form.

Based on the principle of conscious learning, students' speech practice is based on knowledge of the rules and laws of the functioning of the English language, on the basis of assimilation of the meaning of words and forms. At the same time, knowledge about this language, although they should be strong enough, is not an end in itself, they contribute to the development of speech skills and, accordingly, facilitate the practical use of the language in various types of speech activity. This contributes to the birth of a rich world of language, about which the linguist V. von Humboldt: "Through the diversity of language, the richness of the world and the diversity of what we learn in it are revealed to us."

References:

1. Nafasova, D. (2022). TABIIY RESURSLARNI BOSHQARISH, EKOLOGIYA VA ATROF-MUHIT MUHOFAZASI. *Scientific progress*, 3(3), 739-744.
2. Турсунов, Х., & Алибаев, М. А. (2020). Важность обеспечения безопасности наземных транспортных средств. *Life Sciences and Agriculture*, (3-2), 33-36.
3. Hamdam, T. (2022). Theoretical and Methodological Aspects of Community Supervision Instituting. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(9), 80-85.
4. Tursunov, X. T., & Rahimova, T. U. (2006). *Ekologiya*.
5. Турсунов, Х., & Алибаев, М. А. (2020). REQUIREMENTS TO ENSURE THE SAFETY OF GROUND VEHICLES. *Life Sciences and Agriculture*, (3-2), 33-36.
6. Турсунов, Х. КОРХОНАЛАРДА МЕХНАТНИ МУХОФАЗА КИЛИШНИ АСОСИЙ ЧОРА-ТАДБИРЛАРИ ВА УНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШДА КАСАБА УЮШМАЛАРИНИНГ РОЛИ. Хорижий hamkorlar ishtirokida o 'tkazilgan Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani to'plamining TAHRIR XAY'NATI, 607.
7. Habibullaevna, K. C. ., & Hamdam, T. . (2023). Training of the Population in the Field of Civil Defense and Protection against Emergencies. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(3), 17-20.
8. Abdurashid, A. (2023). SANOAT KORXONALARIDA YUK KO 'TARISH MASHINALARINI ISHLATISH TARTIBI VA XAVFSIZ ISHLATISH BO 'YICHA CHORA-TADBIRLAR ISHLAB CHIQISH. *Journal of new century innovations*, 24(3), 46-50.
9. Abdurashid, A., & qizi Xushvaqtova, V. A. (2023). ISH JOYLARIDAGI JAROHATLANISHLARNI OLDINI OLIISH BO'YICHA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 23(3), 173-176.
10. Abduraxmonov, A. A., & Dadabayeva, N. A. (2021). O'TA XAVFLI YUQUMLI KASALLIKLAR VA ULARNING TARQALISHINI OLDINI OLIISH CHORA TADBIRLARI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(3), 340-351.
11. Atakhanovich, Abdurakhmonov A., and Dadaboeva N. Abdurazakovna. "Origin And Protection Of Epidemiological And Episootic Diseases." *JournalNX*, 2021, pp. 744-751.
12. Abdurakhmonov, A. A., & Dadabayeva, N. A. PREVENT SERIOUS INFECTIOUS DISEASES

AND THEIR SPREAD PRECAUTIONARY MEASURES.

13. Abdurashid, A. (2023). Energetik innovatsion poligon tashkil etish. Journal of new century innovations, 20(1), 169-177.

14. Abdurashid, A. (2023). Qayta tiklanuvchi energetika manbai. Journal of new century innovations, 20(1), 178-186.

15. Абдурахмонов А. А., Дадабаева Н. А. ЗАМОНАВИЙ РАҚАМЛИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИНГ ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШ СОҲАЛАРИ ВА ЮТУҚЛАРИ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т.

16. Abdurakhmanov, A., & Usmonov, U. (2023, January). THE PROBLEMS OF AUTOMOBILE ENTERPRISE STUDYING MUD SWEATS AND STORING THEM IN A LAND. In Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences (Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 105-108).

